

ECOLOGICAL TOURISM DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS

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Abstract: According to the information of the "World Tourism and Excursion Council" and "World Tourism Organization" currently, ecological tourism is one of the rapidly developing tourism industries. That is, the share of ecological tourism in the world tourism industry is from 10% to 20%, and the income from ecological tourism services is 55 billion. dollars and its annual growth is 30%. Also, in the future, ecological tourism will become one of the main strategic directions in world tourism, and of course these directions will also enter the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Key words: Ecology, tourism, UN, nature, excursion, resource, environ- ment, UNEP, UNCED

In the world, the direction of ecological tourism in the field of tourism was formed and is developing on the basis of the search for ways to save the nature of our planet and its resources for the prevention of the ecological crisis facing mankind, for the sustainable development and survival of mankind. The planetary ecological problems facing mankind must and must be solved by mankind itself. From this point of view, we will contribute to the timely solution of the issues of ecotourism development in our country, preservation of biodiversity in our nature, protection of our natural resources, and prevention of international environmental crises.

The origin of ecological tourism or the term ecotourism in the world is the increase of global environmental problems in front of human society in the last quarter of the 20th century. During this period, as a result of the increased negative impact of humanity on the natural environment and natural resources, the ecological crisis put on the agenda at the international level the fact that it will be difficult for humanity to live in the planetary regions in the future.

At the end of the 18th - beginning of the 19th century, English tourists traveled to the entire continent of Europe in order to study the culture and history of the local population, as well as to see the wonderful nature. Because the landscapes of the Alps or the mountain forests of the Carpathians are not found in England, they were considered as the main object of tourism. But this tourism is combined with complex tourist routes. Taking into account the British interest in nature tourism, Swiss businessmen organized a nature tourism service as part of "Grand Tour" and it brought huge financial benefits to the organizers. During this period (1913s), natural areas protected by the state were allocated in Switzerland. Although trips to nature reserves are not called ecotourism, they are emerging as "nature-oriented tourism".

In 2001, the Ecotourism Association was established in Russia. 2002 was announced as the "International Year of Ecotourism" by the initiative of the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) and the World Tourism Organization (WTO). On the initiative of these organizations, the World Ecotourism Summit was held on May 19-22, 2002, under the auspices of the Canadian Tourism Commission and the Quebec City Tourism Authority. More than a thousand representatives from the state, non-state and private sectors from 132 countries took part in it. The Quebec Summit was the starting point for a new tourism destination that represented ecotourism on a global scale. He defined the main tactical and strategic tasks of the relevant tourism direction at the World Sustainable Development Summit held in August-September 2002 for the next ten years. The Declaration adopted at the summit was sent to the UN. There are 19 guidelines recommended by the Quebec Declaration to national, regional and local authorities, covering almost all aspects of ecotourism. In the declaration, 14-item recommendations are presented to representatives of the private sector. Most of them guide private companies, tour operators or organizations to organize, manage and ensure environmental safety of ecotourism.

Concluding that the development of ecotourism is one of the best ways to solve the global environmental problems facing humanity, the UN declared 2002 the year of "International Ecotourism". So far, ecotourism has given the expected and expected results in the international community in preserving and protecting the nature of our planet. At this point, it is necessary to mention the international cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in nature protection, ecology and rational use of nature. Thanks to the effective work of the World Tourism Organization (WTO) and the environmental organization "Green World", the "Comprehensive Action Program" of the Concept "Agenda 21 for travel and tourism industry", 21st Century Agenda for the Tourism and Travel Industry ", after the adoption of the "Environment and Development" (UNCED) program, the Republic of Uzbekistan developed its international cooperation strategy in the field of nature protection.

The international cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the use of natural resources and environmental protection is becoming more active year by year. This cooperation is in harmony with the national tasks of our country and future development issues. Until now, the Republic of Uzbekistan is actively participating in international cooperation on the preservation of biological diversity, prevention of global climate change, prevention of ozone layer destruction, preservation of the ecological balance of unique natural regions, use of natural resources based on modern technologies. Since 1992, the Republic of Uzbekistan has been a member of the International Ecological Council of the CIS as an equal member of the UN. Our country adopted and internationally supported the "Environment and Development" declaration adopted by the UN in Brazil in 1992, the "21st Century Agenda for Tourism and Travel Industry" program. Until now, the Republic of Uzbekistan is successfully participating in more than 50 international agreements on nature protection and nature use.

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